

Protonation Constants of Salicylic and Substituted Salicylic Acids

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THE protonation constants of a few substituted salicylic acids have been reported earlier¹⁻³. No

The values of pH at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$ and $\bar{n}_A=1.5$ correspond to the values of pK_2 and pK_1 respectively. Refined values of pK were also obtained by point-wise calculations and linear plot method and are also recorded in Table-1.

The pK_1 value is found to follow the order: SA>SSA>5-NH₂SA>5-CISA>3-NO₂SA>3:5-DNSA in agreement with the inductive effect of the substituents⁶

The results indicate the failure of Hemmett's equation⁶⁻¹⁰.

TABLE-1 pK VALUES FOR SALICYLIC AND SUBSTITUTED SALICYLIC ACIDS

Ligand (Acid)	Half intergal method			Linear plot method			Point-wise calculation average				Average	
	pK_1	pK_2	pK_3	pK_1	pK_2	pK_3	pK_1	pK_2	pK_3	pK_1	pK_2	pK_3
SA	3.15	11.80	-	3.13	11.64	-	3.33	11.76	-	3.20	11.73	-
SSA	1.94*	3.10	-	1.93*	3.07	11.71	1.98*	3.08	11.70	1.95*	3.08	11.70
5-NH ₂ SA	2.80	5.45†	-	2.80	5.43†	10.99	2.72	5.45*	10.96	2.77	5.44†	10.98
5-CISA	2.57	11.63	-	2.62	11.46	-	2.68	11.56	-	2.62	11.55	-
3-NO ₂ SA	2.30	10.35	-	2.35	10.33	-	2.25	10.35	-	2.30	10.34	-
5-NO ₂ SA	2.25	10.79	-	2.25	10.72	-	2.28	10.75	-	2.26	10.75	-
3:5-DNSA	2.08	8.13	-	2.03	8.18	-	2.01	8.21	-	2.04	8.17	-

*for SO₃H and †for NH₃⁺ (the conjugate acid)

attempt seems to have been made to determine the same in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium. The pK values of Salicylic (SA), 5-Sulpho-salicylic (SSA), 5-Amino-salicylic (5-NH₂SA), 5-Chlorosalicylic (5-CISA), 3-Nitro-salicylic (3-NO₂SA), 5-Nitro-salicylic (5-NO₂SA), and 3:5 Di-nitro-salicylic (3:5-DNSA) acids have, therefore, been determined employing Bjerrum's titration technique as reported by Irving and Rossotti⁴. Refined values are then obtained by point-wise calculation and linear plot methods and are reported here.

Experimental :

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. AR grade.

Polymetron model CL-41 pH -meter was used for pH -metric titrations conducted at 30°. Measurements were made with an accuracy of ± 0.05 pH units and the reproducibility of the readings was of the same order.

pH -metric titrations of the solutions of (i) free HClO₄ and (ii) free HClO₄+Ligand (acid) were performed in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium against standard NaOH solution while maintaining the ionic strength at 0.1 M (NaClO₄).

Results

The Irving-Rossotti⁴ expression was used for the calculation of \bar{n}_A values. These in turn were employed for the determination of stepwise dissociation constants of the various salicylic acids used in the present investigation.

The values of pK were calculated by half-integral method making use of formation curves.

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A new Synthesis of 3-Hydroxy-3':4'-Methylenedioxy-Flavone

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IN our investigations on the flavonoids of the indigenous plants, 3-hydroxy-3':4'-methylenedioxy-flavone(II) was needed for comparison. While Hattori¹ prepared it by acid hydrolysis of the oximino derivative of the corresponding flavanone, we herein report an elegant synthesis of the flavonol (II) by the application of Algar Flynn Oyamada (AFO)reaction.

Claisen condensation of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with piperonal afforded the chalcone(I) which was subjected to simultaneous cyclisation and oxidation by alkaline hydrogen peroxide to yield II. The structure was proved by melting point, analysis and spectroscopic data (*vide* Experimental) as well as by preparation of its *o*-methyl and *o*-acetyl derivatives. The NMR spectrum of II deserves special mention. Besides the characteristic signal at τ 3.97 for $-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-$ grouping, spin decoupling by irradiation at H-5' and H-5 indicated that H-6' was ortho coupled to H-5' and meta coupled to H-2'. H-5 was ortho coupled to H-6 and meta coupled to H-7. H-2' was hidden in H-6' signal. H-7 and H-8 signals were overlapped.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. UV spectrum was taken on Varian instrument (model 635). IR and NMR spectra were recorded respectively on Unicam SP 1000 and a Varian A-60 Me NMR (TMS as internal reference) spectrometers. Mass spectrum was taken on A.E.I. spectrometer, (Model MS 9).

2'-Hydroxy-3:4-methylenedioxy-chalcone (I):

o-Hydroxyacetophenone (2.2 ml) and finely powdered piperonal (2.49 g) were mixed. An absolute alcoholic solution (2 ml) of NaOH (2 g) was then added and the mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temp. The orange red sodium salt obtained was acidified with dil. HCl to get the yellow solid, 2'-hydroxy-3:4-methylenedioxy-chalcone recrystallised from alcohol in faint yellowish crystals, m.p. 136-138° (lit.⁸ m.p. 138°); yield 3.4 g (84.1%). Found: C=71.58; H=4.53%. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₂O₄, C=71.64; H=4.48%.

2'-Hydroxy-3':4'-methylenedioxy-flavone (II):

2'-Hydroxy-3:4-methylenedioxy-chalcone (I: 0.73 g) was dissolved in freshly distilled methanol (68 ml) NaOH solution (20 ml, 4*N*) was added dropwise to the cooled solution with occasional shaking and cooling. Hydrogen peroxide solution (9 ml, 18%) was then slowly added to the mixture with light shaking and left overnight at room temp. The intense yellow flocculent solid flavonol(II) that

separated was recrystallised from absolute alcohol in nearly colourless crystals, mp. 212-214° (lit.¹ m.p. 214°); yield 0.68 g (88.5%). Found: C=67.90; H=3.90%; Calc. for C₁₈H₁₀O₈: C=68.1; H=3.55%. λ ethanol max 360 nm, ($\epsilon=42,000$) and 245 nm

($\epsilon=47,000$); ν max 3250 (sharp); 1570(m); 1610 (s); NMR (CDCl₃): τ : 3.97; s, 2H, $-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-$; 1.78, br. d, 1H, $J=7.8$ Hz, H-5; 2.16, br. d, 1H $J=8.0$ Hz, H-6'; 2.25, hidden s, 1H, H-2': 2.42 ill-defined m, 2H, H-7 and H-8; 2.58, br. d, 1H, $J=7.8$ Hz, H-6; 3.06, d, 1H, $J=8.0$ Hz, H-5'. MS: m/e 282 (M⁺, 100%), 281 (M-H, 36%), 254 (M-CO, 10%), 225 (M-CO and CHO, 10%) and 196 (MCO, and 2CHO, 10%). The compound responder to basic lead acetate and Shinoda colour tests. It produced reddish solution with conc. H₂SO₄ acid and brownish violet colour with FeCl₃.

It formed *o*-acetate (III) in colourless needles (ethanol). m.p. 136-137° in the usual way with Ac₂O in pyridine at room temp. left for 2 days. Found: C=66.61; H=3.76%; C₁₈H₁₂O₈ requires C=66.63; H=3.70%.

3':4'-Methylenedioxy-flavonol-*o*-methyl ether:

The flavonol (II) 0.11 g, and K₂CO₃ (2 g), CH₃I (1 ml) in dry acetone (10 ml) were refluxed for 6 hr. Usual work-up yielded a light chrome solid *o*-methylether derivative, recrystallised from ethanol in colourless prisms, m.p. 153° (lit.¹, m.p. 155°); yield 0.09 g (77.9%). Found: C=68.84; H=4.12%; Calc. for C₁₇H₁₂O₈: C=68.92; H=4.05%.

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